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Reframing Engineering Creativity through Meaningful Interdisciplinary Writing

D. S. Ozkan¹

Virginia Tech
Blacksburg, VA, USA

D. Bairaktarova

Virginia Tech
Blacksburg, VA, USA

M. Eodice

University of Oklahoma
Norman, OK, USA

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ABSTRACT

In engineering education, creativity is riddled with ambiguity, so much so that we wonder how to teach it but stray away from open-ended questions that give it room to breathe. In the current of free-market principles, creativity becomes a valuable skill as it can pave the path to profitable technological innovation. Under the influence of psychologists, engineering educators have identified creativity as a necessary skillset for engineering graduates [1]. In this concept paper, we reframe creativity cultivation as a process of reframing knowledge. We focus on writing as a form of manipulating language that undoubtedly reframes knowledge. In its application to engineering problems, writing can serve as a tool of reframing that leads to creative problem solving.

¹ D. S. Ozkan
desenoz@vt.edu

1 INTRODUCTION

Ever since J. P. Guilford's 1950 presidential address to the American Psychological Association on creativity, researchers from a variety of disciplines have taken it upon themselves to distil this amorphous ability into a measurable skill. Creativity as an educational quality is coveted across disciplines as it portends the advancement of fields. Specifically, in US science and technology work, researchers identified the need to increase the creativity of scientists and engineers to stay ahead in the post WWII Cold War era and recover from Sputnik shock in 1957 [2]. At the time there were thoughts that the Soviet advances in technology stemmed from their enhanced creativity [3]. To strengthen their lead in the military and space race, the US increased its federal funding and in doing so tasked researchers in identifying the magic elixir that is creativity.

The context of creativity research at that time was that of global competitiveness following a world war. Across different disciplines, these findings on creativity differed due to their contextual environments. For instance, the social sciences in during the Cold War era experienced a different shift regarding creativity. In response to the rising empiricism in the field, "an interdisciplinary group of Harvard social scientists including the anthropologist Clyde Kluck-hohn and the sociologist Talcott Parsons, co-authored "Toward a Common Language for the Area of the Social Sciences," an influential manifesto for unification of the social sciences" [4, p. 79]. The authors' intentions had been to develop interdisciplinarity through shared language to close the widening gap among fields in social science and foster a more unified, but democratic form of the discipline [4].

Through the Cold War era, the "open mind" principle was also tied to American ideals of liberalism, as the open mind became a form of resistance towards "the rising tide of conformity" [4, p. 6]. By filling in the gaps of "narrow-minded" disciplinarians, a common language can highlight implicit assumptions inherent in the epistemology of social science disciplines. Notions of the open mind served to cultivate tolerance as a push against McCarthyism and the military, both of which represented rigidity and conformity. In education, the open mind supported student curiosity and implemented discovery-based learning as a way for students to push back against controlling structures of pedagogy. A push towards the open mind was a push towards "flexibility, autonomy, and creativity," [4, p. 17].

Understanding the background and context described above helps us consider how creativity has impacted the training of engineers. Through the paper, we discuss research in creativity and the challenges in defining and measuring the construct. We reposition creativity as a form of interdisciplinary framing, by which writing serves as the medium of this reframing. Lastly, we end with recommendations cultivate creativity by practicing reframing through writing.

1.1 Creativity as Context-Dependent

Besides agreeing with the notion that it is both novel and useful, psychologists, social scientists, and education researchers have provided many competing and reductionist approaches to identifying creativity. Research ranges from measuring the creativity of products [5] to the creative identities of people [6] to a cultural notion of creativity [7]–[9]. According to Baillie & Walker, “creativity is a convenient label for what is a quintessentially subjective phenomenon” [10, p. 36]. Although creativity is often regarded as having a universal meaning, contextual factors alter the way the construct is operationalized and applied. Creativity as a phenomenon leaves many researchers with the task of redefining the construct such that each definition fits a slightly different purpose. To this end, these different ‘flavours’ of creativity give rise to a deeper understanding of the priorities and gauges of success in the time or discipline in which specific instances of creativity are lauded. By understanding what makes up creativity in different domains, we can deepen our understanding into what is valued in that time period to that discipline.

In engineering, the product or solution is sought to be more creative, whereas, in fine art, problem finding carries more ‘creative’ weight. These values can change. Galenson asserts that the art world used to value problem-solving in the 19th century but has shifted towards problem finding in more recent years [11]. He gives the example of Picasso and Cezanne, in which their work is valued concerning the time that they were painted. Cezanne’s older paintings are more expensive whereas Picasso’s younger paintings are more valuable. These differences are rooted in the values held by the domain of fine arts at the time [11]. The differences of value held by disparate domains is one barrier to accepting the domain-general view of creativity. Because of the social context in which creativity surfaces, positing that there is one general view of creativity reduces the contextual constraints that give it different forms. However, we would argue that using these differences in contexts outside of their original context is how to achieve both novelty and usefulness in a domain.

In the example of problem-finding as a type of creativity, Getzels and Csikszentmihalyi conducted several studies with art students that showed that those who used more problem-finding also provided more viable solutions [12]. In science and engineering, a focus on problem-finding can similarly result in the addition of novel problems and increased solutions to existing problems that have been reframed, yet without the realization that problem-finding plays an important role in the creative process, shifting what is valued as creative would not be recognized. Because of the different societal implications that the arts possess, problem-finding is stressed more than that in domains like engineering. Through an understanding that different disciplines add different but widely applicable content to the theme of creativity, we can begin to form more encompassing insights that comprise creativity.

1.2 Creativity Cultivation from Other Disciplinary Knowledge

From a constructivist paradigm, learning is a creative process [13], but when training programs are developed to elicit behaviourist responses, the creativity inherent in

learning and consequent transfer cannot take form. One of the major ontological assumptions of creativity underlying domain-specific perspectives is its conflation of domain expertise and creativity applied in a domain. Creativity can manifest in the domain by way of creative problem-solving or individual self-expression. Still, this is not to say the creativity is dependent on domain expertise to flourish. Baer continues to state that expertise could aid pursuits outside of one's field. However, he maintains that this is the "exception, not the rule" [14]. What of the opposite, in which domain expertise is enhanced by the introduction of knowledge from other domains? When extending this issue to that of language, Goethe has written that without knowing a foreign language, one cannot truly know their own language (Goethe cited in Vygotsky, 1986, p. 160). Experimental studies corroborate this claim, which show how children use the tools of language with more deliberation. Vygotsky extends this argument to algebra and arithmetic, in which knowledge of arithmetic enhances that of algebra by turning it into a concrete application of algebraic methods [15, p. 160].

Another facet of creativity that Csikszentmihalyi discusses in his book, *Creativity* is that of 'borrowing' from other disciplines [16]. Multi- and interdisciplinary pedagogy has been used to foster flexible thinking by encouraging students to apply knowledge from other domains to their understanding of the course material [17]. Metaphorical and analogical thinking are two ways used to promote creativity; they emphasize connections between disciplinary content that can ultimately yield the generation of novel and effective solutions. Waller describes one instructor who teaches electrical circuits and draws out his students' ability to use the input/output relationship between signals that is specific to electrical engineering to also explain mechanical components, chemical components, economic components, social psych components and so forth [17]. Research has pointed to ways to help students use analogical thinking describe the "functions of a product (e.g., a design artefact) or process (e.g., a way to measure something, a procedure for solving a complex problem)," with related functions from different domains. From a constructivist paradigm, this process of framing and re-framing concepts enables students to gain a better understanding of concepts, internalization, such that they can use and communicate them in applied work, externalization [15]. Creativity is enhanced by a more comprehensive understanding of domains, which is what metaphorical and analogical teaching strategies provide.

Through metaphor and analogy, researchers use language to expose patterns of science that may not have been evident before [18, p. 153]. In disciplines ranging from computer science to biology, scholars have used local and distant analogies to relate problems outside of their domain to ones in their domain to reach solutions. Because of the implicit definitions in domain language, many of the problems can be overlooked or framed in expected ways; analogical thinking helps divulge the nuances that may come with translating one problem to another domain [19, p. 308]. Moreover, language has been said to mediate our pursuit of knowledge, thus expanding this language to include that of different disciplines will better guide processes of problem finding and solving [20].

In one example, a plant biologist, Monica Gagliano, pushed her field in an ostensibly non-biological direction when she used educational metaphors to explain plant behaviour [21]. Her knowledge of working memory and decision making affected the development of her studies, ranging from evoking a response of fear, then training the plants through experience, and testing whether they recalled this ‘lesson’ up to 28 days later [21]. By recognizing characteristics of working memory and decision making in a field seemingly bereft of such qualities and to the scepticism of her colleagues, Gagliano unveiled a different avenue of plant biology that had previously seemed improbable. As for the transfer of creativity, education and plant biology seem quite far from one another in Sternberg’s spatial multidimensional domain space, yet the recognition of established concepts from one can result in an incredibly creative accomplishment established in the other. Consequently, learning to be creative in another domain might be more accessible when framed as learning cross-disciplinary content.

Csikszentmihalyi offers a plethora of examples of the creativity transfer that exists for deemed ‘creatives’ in his book, *Creativity: Flow and the Psychology of Discovery and Invention* [16]. After interviewing several established writers, he highlights that each of them draws from a wide array of knowledge outside of their domain expertise. Ranging from the knowledge of many languages to the synthesis of music and geometry, to the incorporation of quantum physics and microbiology, each of these writers finds a way to express their creativity by framing “together ideas and emotions from disparate domains” [16, p. 263]. Similarly, when Csikszentmihalyi interviews biologists, he finds that their main goals after having been established in their careers were to synthesize cross-disciplinary knowledge--to connect their domain-expertise to other domains. Jonas Salk, in an interview by Csikszentmihalyi, described that he focuses on intuitive and analogical leaps between the different processes in the arts and sciences. Wilson, another interviewee, focuses on the collinearity between biological and cultural processes and Klein connects biological knowledge across domains that proceed independently, for example, virology, genetics, and oncology [16, p. 289]. By expanding their domain expertise by studying across disciplines, many seek more of a holistic than a linear approach to understanding problems. Commoner, a biologist by training, states that the “prevailing philosophy in academic life is reductionism, which is exactly the reverse of [his] approach to things.” [16, p. 285]. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach to their domain expertise, these researchers embed themselves in a continuous cycle of idea to action through reflection and incorporation of domains seemingly outside of their own. Csikszentmihalyi uses these examples of cross-disciplinary integration to show that studying disciplines can help scholars reframe existing problems or yield diverse solutions.

2 REFRAMING KNOWLEDGE THROUGH WRITING

The notion of reframing that has come up through the research on creativity is a by-product of language itself. Language is a tool that we use to frame ideas. Vygotsky has studied how language is used as a tool in constructing knowledge. Language also

acts as a symbolic system that allows us to transfer and apply this knowledge [15]. Metaphors and analogies are used to reframe disciplinary problems and ideas in other disciplines [22]. For students, the notion of reframing can be cultivated from an emphasis on writing.

Learning already exists as a form of reframing content. Students acquire new knowledge that they then fit into existing mental models; students go through their own process of reframing to build their mental models [24]. Writing can be used to further this process of constructivist learning. According to Janet Emig, in a landmark essay published over twenty years ago, “writing is unique mode of learning... [it] is not merely valuable, not merely special, but unique... Writing is a process of discovery” [7]. In the classroom, students “wrestle with ideas and modify their understanding” of concepts [3, 4]. However, in traditional engineering courses, many of the teaching paradigms are to deliver knowledge through a one-way path from instructor to student. For students to *wrestle* with ideas and *modify* their understanding, the instructor must also understand where students are in their process of knowing to then encourage deeper levels of understanding that allow students to wrestle and modify their knowledge [24].

2.1 Writing in the Engineering Curriculum

In engineering, “writing is viewed as a part of an engineer’s job but not as a part of engineering, which presumably happens in some separate, prior realm” [26, p. 58]. As language is used to shape and mediate disciplinary knowledge, it becomes critical to the creation and application of knowledge. Within the engineering culture, “writing is incidental to the project at hand,” in which the product rather than the document shows the culmination of engineering work [26, p. 61]. But, as Windsor shows, the final product of an engineer may not be perceived as a form of writing, but “it is an essential means by which that product is created because it is the essential means by which engineering knowledge is created” [26, p. 61].

Advocates for writing in engineering courses point to the cultivation of critical thinking skills in students [26], reflective thinking skills which are central to design, [28]–[30] and the ability to adapt knowledge across disciplinary boundaries [22]. But if cultivated intentionally in the engineering classroom, writing can braid the entire engineering process from problem finding to problem solving [23].

One example from UT Austin describes a chemical engineering course that is accompanied by a reflective journal assignment that acts as a form of communication between the instructor and student [30]. The journal is a means for students to come up with analogies of the technical content from the class. The instructor also highlights the most ‘creative’ analogy with a class vote during each class meeting to motivate students to ‘struggle with their analogies and journal entries in order to gain “anonymous” recognition from their instructor and classmates’ [31, p. 144].

Another form of writing that helps students to become more aware of their creative processes is reflection [10], [32]. Reflection offers more ways in which to define and situate engineering problems without immediately proposing solutions. According to

Dym, “design cannot be done in vacuo: independent of context” [33, p. 4]. Ongoing reflection has been shown to aid in the understanding of context as well as offer a platform in which instructors can give formative feedback and also receive feedback on where the students are in their learning [32], [34], [35]. Schön asserts that reflections are a key part of practicing design, for the reflexive designer learns to think of the problem and its environment before possible solutions to understand the situational consequences of a solution [30]. Developing a more critical and holistic stance in which to frame problems also contributes to the ability for students to use flexible thinking which enhances creativity.

3 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Creativity has become wide shoes that we fill with coveted attributes. From constructs leading to success, to flexible thinking, to imagination and curiosity, creativity is constantly flexed in its definitions. Consequently, the essence of what we mean by creativity falls to the social context in which it is housed. In this space, that social context becomes a disciplinary home. Creativity in engineering must take on effective problem finding and solving qualities to yield a novel and useful contribution. Reframing the understanding of these problems and knowledge from other disciplines as novel and useful solutions is a form of creativity. This notion of reframing is a manipulation of language and thought that is pivotal to writing, thus for engineering students to be ‘taught creativity’ perhaps we need to engage them in intentional writing exercises that cultivate this ability to reframe new knowledge into existing mental models.

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